

CONSUMER ACCEPTANCE OF VENDING MACHINE READY-TO-EAT FILIPINO MEALS IN HIGH-TRAFFIC AREAS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate consumer acceptance of ready-to-eat meals in vending machines located in high-traffic areas. Due to the current fast-paced workflow, consumers barely manage to sustain themselves with proper meals; thus, the idea of studying ready-to-eat meals in vending machines arose for accessibility and convenience. The researchers utilized the descriptive-correlational design to assess the significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The researchers gathered the needed data by conducting a survey within the vicinity of PUP Sta. Mesa Manila, both from the students and workers present around the area. The answers showed that there was a moderate relationship between variables in affecting consumer acceptance of ready-to-eat meals. In conclusion, consumers in high-traffic areas accepted the idea of ready-to-eat meals in vending machines and viewed it as acceptable and feasible. The idea of accessible meals was viewed as a convenient addition throughout the high-traffic business and education sector.

Keywords: *ready-to-eat meals, meal accessibility, high-traffic areas, consumer acceptance*

INTRODUCTION

The current state of the world revolves as if time were merely a construct, rapidly evolving, and people are often preoccupied in a fast-paced society. Amongst all things, even necessities such as food require time-efficient alternatives. As technology continuously influences everyday life, consumers have learned how to utilize digital platforms and adapt to modern lifestyles; it has significantly reshaped how Filipinos access and engage with food markets, fostering greater accessibility, convenience, and efficiency. Despite this rapid development in accessibility, individuals who are in a constant rush have few options for the selection of food located in high-traffic areas. One emerging development that meets this need in various countries is vending machines offering various food options that are quick and easy to consume.

According to the study of 6Wresearch (2022), the Philippine market for vending machines has been steadily growing for the past few years due to urbanization and evolving consumer lifestyles. The study also mentions that vending machines offer convenient solutions for quick access to snacks, beverages, and essential items, making them popular in high-traffic areas. The technological advancements of these machines have become prevalent in digitalized payment methods and smart inventory tracking, giving satisfaction to user experience and efficiency.

A recent study shows how vending machines can drive consumer behavior mostly for those who study or work in high-traffic areas. However, vending machine food options raise a similar concern to fast-food chains of unhealthy selection of meals that may lead to health implications in the long run. This study focuses on the feasibility of full ready-to-eat Filipino meals through vending machines catering to people who work in high-traffic areas, offering healthier and time-efficient food options. The researchers also found insights that consumers in today's generation are interested in initiatives to improve the nutritional quality of items available from vending machines, and a statistical result of 80% people are willing to pay for the same number of healthier products. Additionally, including nutritional information at the point-of-purchase boosts consumer acceptance by offering healthier snack or food decisions for vending machine users (Carrad et al. 2015).

Despite this potential to shift consumer demand, fresh modes of offerings are subjected to skepticism, unrealistic demands, and a lack of proper regulatory mandates by law. In accordance with Dancey et al.'s (2025) study, organizations in Australia have enforced regulations for healthier food retail, as the World Health Organization encourages countries to adopt policies relating to healthier food retailers. This shows the complexity of organizations adapting to current trends in the food market while increasing the availability, affordability, and acceptability of healthier foods in retail settings.

Though a set of restrictions exists, healthy vending is being developed and adapting across the world. These gaps can be filled through proper implementations of contracts and management efficiency. Another study by Dancey et al. (2024) suggests that contracts can be an effective solution in managing healthy-enabling food retail environments. By clearly stating the intent of the contract justifies the operative terms and

conditions and enforces proper management in vending retailers, improving operational performance and health standards.

In conclusion, the study aimed to utilize the potential of initiating consumer acceptance of food vending machines that offer healthier food options sourced from local farmers in high-traffic areas by integrating modern vending concepts that respond to Filipino consumer needs for time-efficient and healthier ready-to-go meals in public spaces.

Research Questions

The evolving lifestyle and modernized consumer preferences have created a demand for food options that are quick, affordable, accessible, and healthy. This study aimed to foster a creative option for busy individuals who highly value time efficiency in high-traffic areas. As technology paves its way through significant changes in preparing and serving food, vending machines have the potential to offer ready-to-eat Filipino meals. Despite the popularity of these machines in various countries, their market potential remains stagnant in the Philippine food industry. This study also highlights the potential technological advancements of vending machines as a new channel for accessible sources of RTE food systems.

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex
 - 1.2. Occupation
 - 1.3. Age range
2. How frequently do consumers purchase food in high-traffic areas?
3. What factors affect consumer acceptance in terms of:
 - 3.1. Placement?
 - 3.2. Accessibility?
 - 3.3. Packaging?
 - 3.4 Price?
4. What is the consumers' perception of RTE Filipino vending machine meals in terms of:
 - 4.1. Legal and supply chain factors
 - 4.2 Health and nutrition
5. How do consumers accept the concept of vending machines offering ready-to-eat Filipino meals in high-traffic areas?

Summary of Related Literature

Vending machines have existed for a very long time. From the first modern vending machine that was developed in England in the early 1880s to the smart vending machine that we know now. It continues to innovate, evolve, and advance features because of technological advancements throughout the years. Over the years, various studies explored different factors and aspects of vending machine operations, such as sanitation, hygiene, consumer behavior, and technological advancements. However, research also

notes that cultural taste, trust in machine-made food, and the freshness of the product play a vital role in the consumer's willingness to try and purchase RTE meals.

Most studies share a common finding that convenience, accessibility, and product quality are some of the major factors that influence acceptance of products that are coming from a vending machine. Wani and Saha (2024) and Yusof et al. (2025) both pointed out that vending machines should be in a place where there is high traffic or a busy place where most people go or pass because of the convenience and accessibility to maximize the use of the vending machine. Likewise, Rozman et al. (2025) and Majid et al. (2024) pointed out that food safety and quality control are important to ensure customer satisfaction. Over all the studies, there is a shared conception that technological reliability and public confidence determine how widely vending machines are accepted in society.

Similar to these studies, the researchers' study shares commonalities. Like Yusof et al. (2025), the study recognized the influence of technological innovation in shaping consumer preferences, and, similar to Majid et al. (2024), the study acknowledges the role of sanitation and safety in determining consumer trust. Furthermore, it aligns with Wani and Saha's (2024) perspective on the importance of strategic placement in high-traffic areas to maximize accessibility. However, while earlier studies focused on vending machines in general, the researchers' study applies these insights to a culturally specific context—the consumer acceptance of vending machines offering ready-to-eat Filipino meals. This direction merges the themes of convenience, technology, and cultural identity within the Philippines.

However, some studies focus more on technological advancements and the buying habits of consumers. Like what Yusof et al. (2025) found out, improving the quality of the products will draw more consumers to go to the vending machine since it plays an important role in meeting consumer needs who value efficiency and confidence. On the other hand, De Guzman et al. (2023) proposed to innovate the vending machine by adding an automated petrol pump for a smoother transaction between the customer and the machine. Meanwhile, Garcia's (2023) study focused more on having free access to certain snacks like the ones that were made wholly from vegetables in their vending machines in schools.

Unlike most prior research, the researchers' study focused on how consumers accept the vending machine that offers Ready-to-eat (RTE) meals, especially in high-traffic areas in the Philippines. Moreover, on how vending machine practices comply with health protocols and the involvement and the benefits of the local farmers in vending machines for sustainable and healthy products.

What makes this study unique is its specific focus on consumer acceptance of vending machines' ready-to-eat meals in high-traffic areas. On the contrary to the earlier research conducted, the study explores the integration of local Filipino cuisine into vending machines. By analyzing consumer perceptions and acceptance, the study introduces a culturally relevant and innovative approach that bridges convenience technology with the traditional Filipino meals.

Scope and Delimitations

This research primarily aimed to understand the reception of Filipino consumers to vending machines dispensing ready-to-go hot meals. Ideally, these machines will be placed in areas with high foot traffic, such as public transportation areas, schools, and other densely packed spaces. The data used for this study is strictly limited to existing studies, with a lack of proper clauses within the field itself. With the way of living in urbanized communities being highly time-efficient, this study promotes a quick alternative for obtaining healthy and filling meals rather than patronizing other similar markets with less nutritional value. As far as the study goes, it is limited to the Philippines and high-traffic zones, such as cities, rather than suburban or rural areas. It also delves into factors such as offering convenience, maintaining high food quality, affordable pricing, and sanitary conditions. This study is limited to the perceived reception towards the new and rising market rather than a detailed analysis of vending machines legally, mechanically, and financially. The mention of ready-to-go cooked meals is the base niche for this study, solely focusing on dispensing chilled meals that can be prepared in just one go.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design refers to the overall framework that the researchers may choose; it serves as the blueprint for how the study is set to be conducted. In addition, it integrates all the necessary components of the research that ensure its progress. A well-thought-out research design allows researchers to ensure that the methods used are feasible and coherent (McCombes, 2021; Bhandari, 2021).

This research adopted the descriptive-correlational design approach to describe the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Moreover, this method observes relationships without manipulating the main variables, seeking data to an existential degree (Barooah, 2025). This study used a descriptive-correlational approach as it is aligned with the research's main objective, which aimed to correlate the acceptability of Food Vending Machines in highly urbanized areas and how consumer acceptance plays a crucial role in this dilemma. Independent variables such as (1) Consumer Frequency of Purchasing Food in High-Traffic Areas, (2) Placement, (3) Accessibility, (4) Packaging, (5) Price, (6) Legal and Supply Chain Factors, (7) Health and Nutrition, and (8) Consumer Lifestyle together with the dependent variable, (1) Consumer Acceptance will be integrated and analyzed to determine the significant association of these main variables.

In line with the descriptive-correlational approach, a quantitative approach is used for gathering data to ensure the study is systematic and aligned with the research method primarily used. This approach focuses on numerical and statistical collection of data that deals with logic and numbers, resulting in an objective stance. The data will be gathered using structured research instruments such as survey questionnaires, polls, and general

surveys. The usage of descriptive-correlational together with the quantitative approach will be extensively helpful to determine the relationship between the variables obtained. (Sreekumar, 2023)

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the vicinity of Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Sta. Mesa Campus and the Light Rail Transit Line 2, Pureza station located in Anonas St., Sta. Mesa, Manila 1016. The researchers have chosen these locations due to the dynamic flow of people between them, consisting of students, employees, and commuters who frequently dine in nearby establishments. This setup allows the researchers to analyze behavioral patterns and consumer acceptance through surveys of ready-to-eat vending machine meals within a high-traffic urban environment.

Since the total number of individuals within the area cannot be precisely determined, the researchers have estimated a population of 10,000. To determine the appropriate number of respondents, Slovin's formula was applied with a 5% margin of error and a confidence level of 95%, resulting in a sample size of 385 respondents. Additionally, the researchers intend to use the purposive sampling technique, as the study targets individuals who are frequently exposed to or familiar with vending machines and who may potentially utilize ready-to-eat vending machine meals.

Population and Sampling Scheme

The research's target population is composed of the students, faculty, and other sectors of employees within Polytechnic University of the Philippines–Sta. Mesa campus. The population also includes the rest of the passengers that the Light Rail Transit (LRT) frequently accommodates at Pureza station. Given that the institution has not disclosed a significant number of students in the school year of 2025-2026, and there is no significant data available to gather on the population of the passengers in LRT Pureza station, the researchers carefully estimated and considered a population of 10,000. This study will use a purposive sampling technique–this technique is also known as a non-probability technique, which is fundamental, especially in qualitative and mixed methods, because it mainly deals with an in-depth understanding of the subject (Tajik et al., 2025).

Slovin's formula is used to compute the sample, which consists of the totality of the population, confidence level, and margin of error. This research applied the confidence level of 95%, which implies that the computed data from this sample shall present a result within its confidence level.

The sample is computed by:

$$\begin{aligned}n &= \frac{N}{(1 + Ne^2)} \\n &= \frac{10,000}{(1 + 10,000(0.05)^2)} \\n &= \frac{10,000}{(1 + 10,000(0.0025))} \\n &= \frac{10,000}{26} \\n &= 384.61 \approx 385\end{aligned}$$

The formula calculated a total of 385 participants, where N is the total population, n is the computed sample, e is the margin of error, and 1 is a constant.

Respondents of the Study

In this study, data will be gathered from students, employees, and commuters within the vicinity of Polytechnic University of the Philippines–Sta. Mesa campus and Light Rail Transit (LRT) Pureza Station. These respondents were identified as the primary participants of this study since they regularly frequent high-traffic areas where food options are scarce and are encompassed by time constraints and unfavorable placements of food establishments. Their participation is intended to provide meaningful perspectives on the vending machine's efficiency, accessibility, convenience, and the overall acceptance of its functionality as a dispenser of ready-to-eat (RTE) meals.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data gathering, or otherwise known as the data collection process, is a significant process of research that is done to procure a proper result and discussion. This area outlines the summary of the step-by-step process of gathering the data for the basis of analysis. The type of data collection utilized will be a printed form or a questionnaire that involves a four (4) point Likert scale. This means that every question has multiple choices, ranging from *agree*, *strongly agree*, *disagree*, and *strongly disagree*. This questionnaire is designed to properly identify the acceptance of consumers regarding dispensing RTE (*ready-to-eat*) meals.

First, the researchers obtained the professor's permission before analyzing and developing a research questionnaire. Second, the researchers formed a criterion for the respondents, such as 1) an Employee or Commuter. 2.) Within the bounds of *Pureza* station. Third, the researcher provides a consent form, stating the purpose of the study, and asking whether these respondents are willing to participate in the study. Fourth, to ensure the participant's willingness to participate, the researchers must retrieve the consent form from the said participants. Fifth, if the participant is willing, the researchers can now distribute their questionnaire and start the data collection.

These processes were followed thoroughly and sequentially for efficiency and accuracy. The process was a lengthy feat of revisions and re-analyzing statements and comments

given by the professor before proceeding to the actual act of gathering data. Additionally, forming the set of questions included in the questionnaire required proper analysis of the needed variables and the sample size of the respondents.

Research Instrument

The researchers decided to use survey questionnaires as the method of gathering data for the research. This will serve as the main research instrument in accordance with the research. In this survey, printed questionnaires answerable by pen are implemented to observe real-time results. Moreover, the incorporation of related studies and literature will be performed to ensure accuracy and relevance.

This survey questionnaire consists of statements answerable in a 4-point Likert scale, with numerical data ranging from 1 to 4. This gives researchers accurate data that is used to determine the consumer acceptance of food vending machines in high-traffic areas. In line with that, the survey consists of different statements relative to the variables of the Vending Machine Distribution Model, such as price, accessibility, and eating habits, that determine the acceptability of a Food Vending Machine. The Likert scale limits its response to very highly acceptable, highly acceptable, acceptable, and not acceptable at all. Refer to the figure below the mean scale:

Table No. 1 Interpretation Scale for Likert Scale

Descriptive Rating	Point Value	Mean Scale
Very Highly Acceptable	4	4.00 - 3.26
Highly Acceptable	3	3.25 - 2.51
Acceptable	2	2.50 - 1.76
Not Acceptable at all	1	1.75 - 1.00

The study chose to rely on the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) as the method to determine the relationship between each variable. Standard variables such as Packaging and Price, which are composed of three (3) questions and four (4), as the highest score based on the Likert scale, has a maximum score per construct of 12, which aligns the same in a 12-point range, making them comparable at the same time. These results for all the frequency variables are to have a continuous ordinal-to-interval hybrid scale, making it acceptable for Pearson's r . In line with that, the scale parity of the variables is coherently linear with the variable structure because of the independent variables' alignment with the Likert scale's maximum score per construct. This makes each variable comparable and equal to each other's, creating an accurate numerical and statistical tabulation.

Table No. 2 Interpretation Scale— Guildford Rule of Thumb

<i>r</i>	Strength of Relationship
< .2	Negligible Relationship
.2 - .4	Low Relationship
.4 - .7	Moderate Relationship
.7 - .9	High Relationship
> .9	Very High Relationship

This survey questionnaire is divided into two (2) parts:

Part I. Non-disclosure and Confidentiality Agreement. This section serves as part of the research ethics. It contains the declarative statements of non-disclosure and confidentiality agreement that will be used to protect the identity and information the respondent provided.

Part II. Food Vending Machine’s Consumer Acceptance in High-Traffic Areas. This section serves as the main part of a survey questionnaire consisting of all questions to determine the acceptability of food vending machines. This consists of six (6) parts, starting with Part I, Demographic Profile, which serves as the researcher’s basis for the respondent’s information. Part II. Consumer Frequency of Purchasing Food in High-Traffic Areas assesses the consumer’s frequency in high-traffic areas. Part III. Vending Machine Distribution Model is divided into three (4) subsections, namely (1) Placement, (2) Accessibility, (3) Packaging, and (4) Price. Part IV Consumer Perception contains two (2) subsections, namely (1) Legal and Supply Chain Factors and (2) Health and Nutrition. Lastly, Part V. Consumer Lifestyle and Acceptance contains two (2) subsections.

Instrument Reliability

The researchers performed reliability testing on the research instrument using Cronbach’s alpha to measure its internal consistency before conducting the survey. The researchers conducted a pilot test to at least thirty (30) consumers within the vicinity of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Sta. Mesa Campus. The results of which were processed through a statistical program that automates the calculation of the Cronbach’s Alpha. Based on the reliability test, Cronbach’s Alpha resulted in **more than 0.70 for all the eight (8) constructs of the questionnaire.** A Cronbach’s score higher than 0.70 indicates that the internal consistency of the instrument is either acceptable, good, or excellent (refer to Table 3.3). A report supporting the use of the test statistics can be found in Appendix D of this paper. Thus, the research instrument, in its entirety, is deemed reliable for research use and data gathering as far as the aforementioned study variables are concerned.

Below is the interpretation scale for Cronbach's alpha: (Saidi & Siew, 2019)

Table No. 3 Interpretation Scale for Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
0.90 and above	Excellent
0.80 - 0.89	Good
0.70 - 0.79	Acceptable
0.60 - 0.69	Questionable
0.50 - 0.59	Poor

Specifically, placement ($\alpha = 0.8738$), price ($\alpha = 0.8409$), and acceptance ($\alpha = 0.8631$) are the three (3) constructs that reported an acceptable level of internal consistency, while accessibility, packaging, legal, health, and lifestyle obtained a coefficient of 0.838, 0.811, 0.837, 0.832, and 0.822, respectively, leading to good internal consistency.

Below is the summary of the Cronbach's scores:

Table No. 4 Summary of Cronbach's Alpha Scores

Construct	Cronbach's alpha	Remark
Placement	0.772	Acceptable
Accessibility	0.838	Good
Packaging	0.811	Good
Price	0.785	Acceptable
Legal	0.837	Good
Health	0.832	Good
Lifestyle	0.822	Good

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected from the respondents was analyzed and interpreted using the following statistical tools and formulas. To assess the level of consumer acceptance of vending-machine ready-to-eat (RTE) Filipino meals and the correlation between influencing factors such as accessibility, affordability, packaging, and consumer lifestyle, these tools were chosen in accordance with the descriptive-correlational design of the study.

1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution

Used to present the **SOP 1**. demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their sex, occupation, age range, and **SOP 2**. frequency of food purchases in high-traffic areas.

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

P = percentage
 f = frequency of responses
 N = total number of respondents

2. Weighted Mean

Used to calculate the average responses of the respondents to each statement in terms of **SOP 3**. placement, accessibility, packaging, price, and **SOP 4**. legal and supply-chain factors, together with health and nutrition.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

\bar{x} = weighted mean
 $\sum fx$ = sum of weighted responses
 N = total number of respondents

3. Likert Scale

Used to discern the level of acceptability of vending-machine ready-to-eat (RTE) Filipino meals as perceived by the consumers based on their assessments: very highly acceptable, highly acceptable, acceptable, not acceptable.

Table No. 5 Interpretation Scale for Likert Scale

Descriptive Rating	Point Value	Mean Scale
Very Highly Acceptable	4	4.00 - 3.26
Highly Acceptable	3	3.25 - 2.51
Acceptable	2	2.50 - 1.76
Not Acceptable at all	1	1.75 - 1.00

4. Ranking

Used to identify the highest and lowest weighted point value among the participants' responses on the statements provided in the survey questionnaire per variable.

5. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r)

Used to determine whether there is a significant correlation in **SOP 5**. between the independent variables, such as (1) Consumer Frequency in High-Traffic Areas, (2) Placement, (3) Accessibility, (4) Packaging, (5) Price, (6) Legal and Supply Chain

Factors, (7) Health and Nutrition, and (8) Consumer Lifestyle, and the dependent variable, (1) Consumer Acceptance.

$$r = \frac{N \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[N \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][N \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

r = correlation coefficient
x = independent variable scores
y = dependent variable scores
N = number of respondents

Table No. 6 Interpretation Scale — Guildford Rule of Thumb

<i>r</i>	Strength of Relationship
< .2	Negligible Relationship
.2 - .4	Low Relationship
.4 - .7	Moderate Relationship
.7 - .9	High Relationship
> .9	Very High Relationship

The study chose to rely on the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (*r*) as the method to determine the relationship between each variable.

RESULTS

This area includes the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data collated from the survey regarding Consumer Acceptance of Vending Machine Ready-to-Eat Filipino Meals in High-Traffic Areas. This area presents an extensive discussion and in-depth analysis of findings using applicable statistical procedures.

Profile of the Respondents

The study collected data from 385 respondents. The demographic distribution is shown in the tables below.

Table No. 7 Sex Distribution

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	220	57.14285714

Male	165	42.85714286
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According to Table No. 7, 220 or 57.14285714% of the respondents were female, and 165 or 42.85714286% were male. Therefore, the majority of our respondents were female.

Table No. 8 Occupation Distribution

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Student	298	77.4025974
Employee	87	22.5974026

According to Table No. 8, a great majority of the respondents are students, which has 298 or 77.4025974% and a great number of respondents are employees, which has 87 or 22.5974026%.

Table No. 9 Age Distribution

Age Range	Frequency	Percentage
12-17	6	1.558441558
18-28	369	95.84415584
29-44	9	2.337662338
45-60	1	0.25974026

Table No. 9 shows that the age range, 18-28 years old, is the highest with 369 or 95.84415585%, next is the age range of 29-44 years old with 9 or 2.337662338%, then 12-17 years old with 6 or 1.558441558%, and lastly is 45-60 years old with 1 or 0.25974026%.

Table No. 10 Frequency of Food Purchase Distribution

Frequency	Count	Percentage
Daily	122	31.68831169
Weekly	133	34.54545455
1-2 times a week	105	27.27272727
Rarely	25	6.493506494

According to Table No. 10, weekly has the highest with 133 or 34.54545455%, next is daily with 122 or 31.68831169%, then 1-2 times a week with 105 or 27.27272727%, and lastly rarely with 25 or 6.493506494%.

Factors Affecting Consumer Acceptance - Overall Means

The following table shows the overall mean for each variable and its descriptive rating based on the Likert scale provided in the methodology.

Table No. 11 Overall Variable Means and Descriptive Ratings

Variable	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Frequency	2.914285714	Highly Acceptable
Placement	3.27012987	Very Highly Acceptable
Accessibility	3.495238095	Very Highly Acceptable
Packaging	3.825974026	Very Highly Acceptable
Price	3.554112554	Very Highly Acceptable
Legal and Supply Chain Factors	3.812121212	Very Highly Acceptable
Health and Nutrition	3.672727273	Very Highly Acceptable
Lifestyle	3.521212121	Very Highly Acceptable
Acceptance	3.665800866	Very Highly Acceptable

Table No. 11 shows that all variables were rated as “Very Highly Acceptable“, except for frequency, which was “Highly Acceptable.” The highest mean in the table is for packaging with 3.825974026, followed by legal with 3.812121212, and health with 3.672727273, showing that these factors were the most valued by respondents. The lowest mean was frequency with 2.914285714.

Ranking Distribution of Variable Ratings

The ranking distribution between each variable was highlighted. The table below indicates the highest and lowest rates per category, together with their frequency.

Table No. 12 Ranking Distribution (Highest - Lowest)

Variable	Highest Rate	Frequency	Lowest Rate	Frequency
Frequency	12	122	3	25

Placement	12	93	4	2
Accessibility	12	160	3	2
Packaging	12	294	3	2
Price	12	140	5	3
Legal and Supply Chain Factors	12	299	3	1
Health and Nutrition	12	217	3	1
Lifestyle	12	152	5	2
Acceptance	12	201	6	6

Table No. 12 shows the ranking distribution per category of each variable. The highest rate given all throughout was 12, with 299 frequency and the lowest rate given was 3, having 1 as its frequency.

Correlation Between Variables (Pearson r)

Pearson product-moment correlation coefficients were computed between each independent variable and consumer acceptance. The table below summarizes the results (r, t statistic, p-value, and interpretation).

Table No. 13 Results of Correlation Analysis

Variable		Pearson r	t Statistic	p-Value (Two-tailed)	Interpretation
Frequency Acceptance	vs.	0.424217539	9.167916025	2.99798E-18	Moderate
Placement Acceptance	vs.	0.442974515	9.66966137	6.19844E-20	Moderate
Accessibility Acceptance	vs.	0.562571392	13.31691121	1.62756E-33	Moderate
Packaging Acceptance	vs.	0.431732991	9.36714807	6.52262E-19	Moderate
Price vs. Acceptance		0.45249641	9.930325999	7.87601E-21	Moderate
Legal and Supply Chain Factors vs. Acceptance		0.492267866	11.06777076	6.84057E-25	Moderate

Health and Nutrition vs. Acceptance	0.501426154	11.34199979	6.64146E-26	Moderate
Lifestyle vs. Acceptance	0.6078607	14.98162968	2.91576E-40	Moderate

Table No. 13 shows the moderate positive correlation between all the variables and their acceptance. Lifestyle with 0.6078607 in r has the strongest relationship with acceptance, while frequency with 0.424217539 in r shows the weakest.

Table No. 14 Result of Hypothesis Testing

Variable	Pearson r	Interpretation	Results
Frequency vs. Acceptance	0.424217539	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Significant (Reject H₀)</i>
Placement vs. Acceptance	0.442974515	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Significant (Reject H₀)</i>
Accessibility vs. Acceptance	0.562571392	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Significant (Reject H₀)</i>
Packaging vs. Acceptance	0.431732991	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Significant (Reject H₀)</i>
Price vs. Acceptance	0.45249641	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Significant (Reject H₀)</i>
Legal and Supply Chain Factors vs. Acceptance	0.492267866	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Significant (Reject H₀)</i>
Health and Nutrition vs. Acceptance	0.501426154	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Significant (Reject H₀)</i>
Lifestyle vs. Acceptance	0.6078607	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Significant (Reject H₀)</i>

Table No. 14 shows that all the variables have a moderate positive relationship with acceptance and are statistically significant, which rejects the null hypothesis (H₀) and accepts the alternative hypothesis (H_a). The table also shows that each factor has a significant influence on acceptance.

DISCUSSION

This area presents the summary of findings resulting from data analysis on the level of

consumer acceptance of Vending Machine Ready-to-Eat Filipino Meals in High-Traffic Areas for day-to-day commuters. The conclusions were derived from the key findings regarded as vital to the research questions. Recommendations were drawn in accordance with the results and discussion of findings, determining the market demand for Food Vending Machines.

Restatement of the Research Question

The evolving lifestyle and modernized consumer preferences have created a demand for food options that are quick, affordable, accessible, and healthy. This study aimed to foster a creative option for busy individuals who highly value time efficiency in high-traffic areas. As technology paves its way through significant changes in preparing and serving food, vending machines have the potential to offer ready-to-eat Filipino meals. Despite the popularity of these machines in various countries, their market potential remains stagnant in the Philippine food industry. This study also highlights the potential technological advancements of vending machines as a new channel for accessible sources of RTE food systems.

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex
 - 1.2. Occupation
 - 1.3. Age range
2. How frequently do consumers purchase food in high-traffic areas?
3. What factors affect consumer acceptance in terms of:
 - 3.1. Placement?
 - 3.2. Accessibility?
 - 3.3. Packaging?
 - 3.4 Price?
4. What is the consumers' perception of RTE Filipino vending machine meals in terms of:
 - 4.1. Legal and supply chain factors
 - 4.2 Health and nutrition
5. How do consumers accept the concept of vending machines offering ready-to-eat Filipino meals in high-traffic areas?

Summary of Findings

Based on the presentation and discussion of data, the following important findings are summarized below:

Consumer Acceptance of Vending-Machine Ready-To-Eat Filipino Meals in Terms Of:

Frequency

On average, both students and employees have high acceptability among consumers

who prefer to dine in high-traffic areas, obtaining a mean weighted average of 2.914285714, respectively. According to the highest weighted mean, the frequency of consumer preferences who dine in high-traffic areas creates a demand for their willingness to try food vending machines. The finding suggests that despite the number of consumers who do not often dine in high-traffic areas, both consumers highly accept ready-to-eat Filipino food vending machines in areas with high foot traffic.

Placement

On average, both students and employees have very high acceptability when it comes to placing food vending machines near schools, terminals, and convenience stores, obtaining a mean weighted average of 3.27012987, respectively. According to the highest weighted mean, both consumers prefer food vending machines to be found near foot-traffic areas is very highly acceptable. The finding suggests that food vending machines that are placed in areas that are easily found are very highly accepted for consumer preference to try ready-to-eat Filipino food vending machines in high-traffic areas.

Accessibility

On average, both students and employees have very high acceptability of food vending machines that are accessible in high traffic areas, obtaining a mean weighted average of 3.495238095, respectively. According to the highest weighted mean, neither consumer do not have any concerns when it comes to accessible ready-to-eat food options near schools, terminals, and convenience stores. The finding suggests that the accessibility of food vending machines with long operating hours and an easy navigation for the user interface is highly accepted by consumers who dine in high-traffic areas.

Packaging

On average, both students and employees have very high acceptability when it comes to the packaging of food vending machines, obtaining a mean weighted average of 3.825974026, respectively. According to the highest weighted mean, both consumers very highly accept ready-to-eat food vending machines with proper packaging. The finding suggests that keeping the food fresh, eco-friendly, and providing nutritional information through its packaging are highly acceptable for consumers who dine in high-traffic areas.

Price

On average, both students and employees have very high acceptability when it comes to the pricing of food vending machines, obtaining a mean weighted average of 3.554112554, respectively. According to the highest weighted mean, both consumers do not have any concerns about the food pricing of ready-to-eat Filipino food vending machines if it's fair and reasonable. The finding suggests that having the right price for reasonable meal planning of food vending machines is very highly acceptable for consumers who dine in high-traffic areas.

Legal and Supply Chain Factors

On average, both students and employees have very high acceptability in legal and supply chain factors of ready-to-eat food vending machines, obtaining a mean weighted average of 3.812121212, respectively. According to the highest weighted mean, both consumers prefer food vending machines if they comply with safety standards, visible business permits, and proper inventory is highly acceptable. The finding suggests that ensuring safety and legal protocols for food vending machines is highly acceptable for consumers who dine in high-traffic areas.

Health and Nutrition

On average, both students and employees have very high acceptability towards the health and nutrition of ready-to-eat Filipino food vending machines, obtaining a mean weighted average of 3.672727273, respectively. According to the highest weighted mean, both consumers greatly prefer ready-to-eat Filipino food that offers healthy food options. The finding suggests that offering freshly stocked and promoting healthy eating habits is very highly acceptable for consumer preference to try ready-to-eat Filipino food vending machines in high-traffic areas.

Consumer Lifestyle

On average, both students and employees have a very high acceptability of consumer lifestyle to try ready-to-eat Filipino food vending machines in high-traffic areas, obtaining a mean weighted average of 3.521212121, respectively. According to the highest weighted mean, both consumers very highly accept food vending machines that offer quick, accessible, and healthy food options. The finding suggests that food vending machines that offer heating features and are time-efficient are very highly acceptable for consumer preference in trying ready-to-eat Filipino food vending machines in high-traffic areas.

Analysis of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Between Each Independent Variable and Consumer Acceptance

Based on the computed value of the Pearson correlation, all of the given variables showed a moderate relationship in accordance with the level of acceptance of ready-to-eat meals in vending machines; all variables were labeled as moderate based on the terms of the Guildford Rule of Thumb. The given variables such as Frequency ($r= 0.424$), Placement ($r= 0.443$), Accessibility ($r= 0.562$), Packaging ($r= 0.431$), Price ($r= 0.452$), Legal ($r= 0.492$), Health ($r= 0.501$), and Lifestyle ($r= 0.607$). All of the pre-mentioned variables were found and equated to have moderate correlations with consumer acceptance. These results mean that the aforementioned variables are associated with a slight increase in acceptance, and that despite this, the increase will not necessarily be excessive. Furthermore, the p-values of the given variables are less than that of the level of significance, which is $\alpha = 0.05$. Due to this, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the variables is rejected.

In summary, the survey respondents' answers and equated results suggest that Frequency, Accessibility, Packaging, Price, Legal, Health, and Lifestyle, which stand as variables for consumer acceptance, do actually play a factor in influencing acceptance. While it is found to be moderate, the results negate the claim of having no significant value, since these variables have a role in affecting consumer acceptance. This shows that focusing on these areas will still prove to be important factors in influencing acceptance levels of ready-to-eat food in vending machines located in high-traffic areas in the Philippines.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the supposed idea of implementing Vending Machine Ready-to-Eat (RTE) Filipino Meals in high traffic areas proved to be acceptable and feasible to the market. The collected data perceived from the point of view of students and employees showed a high acceptance rate of RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machines, as it showed a potential to create a fast and reliable way of making food easier to consume. The RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine has become a great way for busy individuals to consume meals while integrating factors such as time management, nutritional content, and affordable price. Moreover, the reliability of the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine has opened opportunities for Filipino local farmers to export their products to different regions of the Philippines. In this case, the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine helped both busy individuals in urban areas and local farmers in rural areas, creating a mutual cycle of transaction, benefiting both populations. The eight (8) key identifying factors: Frequency, Placement, Accessibility, Packaging, Price, Legal and Supply Chain Factors, Health & Nutrition, and Consumer Lifestyle, which had been meticulously gathered, served as the basis for how the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine positioned itself in the market. According to the data gathered, consumers such as employees and students emerged as highly frequent in high-traffic areas, creating a massive demand for quick and reliable food sources. These consumers always navigate in high traffic areas such as vehicle stations, schools, and terminals, which corresponds to the high acceptance in terms of placement. As a result, the accessibility became highly acceptable due to the linear disposition of the placement of the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine. Moreover, the consumers' acceptance of packaging became highly acceptable, contributing to the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine. Price has also become one of the most highly accepted factors since its consumers are mostly students and employees from busy areas. On the other hand, Legal and Supply Chain Factors—a highly crucial part of the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine, fortunately, got a high acceptance rate despite its complications and technicalities. Lastly, Health and Nutrition were also one of the mediating factors since it is the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine's competitive advantage. Despite this, the consumers' continuous need for innovation and healthy options became the key drivers for it to have a high acceptance rate. The official implementation of the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machines became highly congested due to its convenience and reliability. Consumers from different populations, such as employees and students, had an efficient experience while using the machine. The machine showed a high performance in cleanliness, accessibility, and convenience, which satisfied most of the consumers. It was efficient in terms of dispensing the food products and reliable because

of the packed meals it offered, which mostly consisted of nutritional components. Overall, the machine was excellent and was in proper condition to cater to the needs of every employee and student in high-traffic areas.

Recommendations

For Consumers. The Ready-to-Eat (RTE) Filipino Meals Vending Machine is highly recommended to students as it serves an efficient, reliable, and affordable way of purchasing meals in high-traffic areas. It allows students and employees who often rely on fast-food chains as their quick way to consume food to have a different cycle of eating their food more conveniently. This also allows consumers to have a wide variety of options, such as fruits, vegetables, white meat, and red meat, that serve as a proper diet for every consumer who purchases. The efficiency of the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine served consumers positively in many aspects.

For Entrepreneurs. The Ready-to-Eat Filipino Meals Vending Machine is also immensely helpful for entrepreneurs, especially for the local entrepreneurs who will become the main source of the food options coming from the vending machines. The idea of sourcing out from local entrepreneurs is a good starting point to bridge connections and transactions between two or more business parties. This will serve as a mutually beneficial transaction for everybody in business, included such as farmers, etc. With the wide implementation of the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine, entrepreneurs from local regions of the country will benefit from each other as they serve the majority of the serviceable population.

For the Government. The Ready-to-Eat Filipino Meals Vending Machine serves as a starting point for the government from which to assess the food distribution of the country's population. As of 2023, 96.9% of the country's population are employees, while over 23 million are elementary to senior high school students. With this massive amount of population at stake, the government is bound to make solutions and protocols regarding the food safety and intake of every individual. In line with this, the RTE Filipino Meals Vending Machine serves as a guideline for the government to implement proper food distribution systems in and out of schools and corporate establishments.

For Future Researchers. The results of this study are directed towards future researchers who will undertake the same research topic someday. This paper is recommended to be integrated as one of the researchers' key findings alongside other research and articles in the future for those who will pursue the same interest. This paper also serves as a guide for future researchers who plan to venture into the same idea of implementing vending machines as their subject of study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research ethics serve as a protection for the respondents of the study. This area of the study aimed to show awareness of their safety and privacy, ensuring that their answers are used in a safe and conducive manner, beneficial only to the researchers and

the study. As part of the ethics, areas like confidentiality and respondent privacy in ordinance with the *Republic Act No. 10173*. It is not only the privacy of the respondents that the researchers aim to preserve, but also the clarity, neatness, and honesty of the work itself, to become a guide for future generations. The following areas are practices utilized by the researchers to ensure this part of the study:

Privacy. Above all, privacy is of utmost importance for the researchers. All necessary answers will promptly adhere to the *Data Privacy Act of 2021*, ensuring that respondents involved will maintain their much-needed confidentiality. Any data or information gathered by the researchers shall not be revealed or disclosed beyond the use and purpose of data gathering to achieve necessary results.

Paraphrasing. Paraphrasing is the action of reading a text or a study and rewriting it while integrating one's own perception or view of the said study. Paraphrasing is an important tool for researchers as it adheres to the rules of the *Republic Act No. 8293, Section 176. (Intellectual Property Code)* To a researcher, paraphrasing must not be overlooked to ensure one's own understanding of the given subject matter.

These sets of ethics were utilized by the researchers before, during, as well as after the data gathering procedure. Fostering these actions shows the authenticity and morality of the researchers involved in the process. The researchers promptly followed these ethics to avoid breaching any given law.

Formatting. The researchers follow the proper format and guidelines of research. APA or also known as the American Psychological Association style, specifically the *APA 7th Edition*, is followed by the researchers, utilizing this as a reference. APA style provides a proper layout and formatting to ensure a neat and well-formatted study.

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